

FACTORS AFFECTING THE INVESTMENT DECISIONS OF LIC POLICYHOLDERS IN COIMBATORE

¹Dr.T.Kavipriya & ²Ms. Shalini. S

¹Assistant Professor, Department of Commerce, PSG College of Arts & Science, Coimbatore

²Ph.D Research Scholar, Department of Commerce, PSG College of Arts & Science, Coimbatore

ABSTRACT: Wide spread of awareness on the term LIC is very particular and especially to the rural as they backward in certain reasons, to socially responsible ones and economically backward classes on a view to reach them by insuring them with a mind of spreading awareness by securing life of each people at a financially stabled coverage against death at an affordable cost. Insurance's main goal is to minimize the possibilities of uncertainty and managing loss of accidents. It is the process of substituting the premium payment which is of small concern to a known fee for the professional insurer in exchange medium of assumption of risking low, payment under promise event of loss. Customers are gaining their form of savings in investing and they are being held at the position of securing themselves in making their form of investment decision on any insurance.

Keywords: LIC, investment, economy, awareness, risk, security

INTRODUCTION

The oldest and fastest-growing state-owned insurance provider in India is the Life Insurance Corporation of India (LIC). Since its inception in 1956, LIC has been a key player in the nation's insurance market, providing millions of policyholders the choice of a broad range of life insurance products. For individuals and their families all over India, LIC has become a pillar of financial stability owing to its enormous range of branches and agents. Recognized for its trustworthiness and authority, LIC has made a major contribution to the social welfare and economic development of the whole nation. The company's role as one of the leaders in the field of insurance has been strengthened by its commitment to catering to all of the requirements of its policyholders.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Yash Sharma & Kausik Mukherjee (2016), analyzed the factors which are affecting investor's decision due to which investors incline towards insurance schemes. To suggest for the increase of the trend of taking life insurance by maximum people. Further, there is a lot of scope of growth of investment in the life insurance policy, but insurance companies are required to increase advertisement and more awareness is required to bespread among the people.

Ravi Kumar Tati, Ernest Beryl B Baltazar (2018), identified that there is any association between annual income of investors and factors influencing consumer choice of investment in life insurance. The study concluded that there is no such association. Themajor influencing factors in choosing an insurance company in the future are supposed to be investor relationships, company image and at lower premium.

Prakruthi M.V (2020) examined the objectives are to distribute Health Insurance in rural areas and backward economic and economic sectors with the aim of reaching out to all the most vulnerablepeople in the country and providing them with adequate mortality if it is costly, increase the promotion of personal savings by making insurance-related savings more attractive. The study also aimed to know the schemes, policies, and their impact on the learning environment. The success of LIC Life Business is assessed by various parameters such as new business growth, business performance, business product benefits etc.

D. Sneha (2021) understood and compared the rural and urban policy holder's perceptions towards Life insurance in Warangal division. The insurance market in India is highly concentrated with the Life Insurance Corporation of India (LIC) havingmore than 70% of the market share. High levels of financial illiteracy lead to significant information asymmetry in the market. There is a need for greater education and awareness programs for consumers in this rapidly growing industry.

Manish Dadhich (2022) determined by an old age method of sharing risk through economic cooperation led to the development of the concept of insurance. Life insurance is universally acknowledged as an institution that eliminates risk, substituting certainty for uncertainty and comes to the timely aidof the family in unfortunate events. The insurance industry is the backbone of the economy and plays a dynamic role in providing one of the most vital services needed for the nation's rapid growth. In India, the insurance sector was nationalized with an objective to reach every sphere of this country.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Investment design of Life insurance corporation (LIC) is crucial for the development of economy. LIC is the largest insurance provider and has wide range of investments in the form of long- term and short-term investments. Decisions taken for making investment are complex and vital in nature, as they come with significant effect on the financial outcomes of individuals and business. The study states and identifies the various factor influencing LIC's investment decisions and the effectiveness of its investment policies. It helps in understanding the factors driving LIC's investment decisions, the risk which is associated

with the investments and its optimizing returns.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

Following are the objectives of the study

- To identify the purpose of investment in LIC by the customers.
- To determine various factors influencing customer's investment decision on LIC.
- To investigate the insurance policies that is preferred by the customers.
- To analyze the investment patterns formatted in LIC policies.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research methodology is a way to systematically solve the research problems. This method comprises the following research design; sampling method; sampling size; collection of data methods; analysis tools; and limitation of the study.

Sampling Method	Convenient sampling technique
Sampling size	200 respondents
Area of the study	Coimbatore city
Methods of Data Collection	Both Primary and Secondary Data
Tool for Analysis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Percentage Analysis • Weighted Average Score • Rank Analysis
Limitations of the Study	The study has been conducted from 200 respondents in Coimbatore city, however adequate care has been taken in collecting the unbiased data.

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATIONS

Table 1 – Demographic Profile

Particulars	No. of respondents	Percentage
Gender of the respondents		
Male	105	52.5%
Female	95	47.5%
Age of the respondents		
Below30 years	125	62.5%
31-40 years	41	20.5%
41-50 years	30	15%
Above 51 years	04	2%
Educational level of the respondents		
No formal education	07	3.5%
SSLC/HSC	23	11.5%
Diploma	19	9.5%
UG/PG	130	65%
Professional	21	10.5%
Occupation of the respondents		
Self employed	44	22%
Private Employee	68	34%

Government employee	51	25.5%
Others	37	18.5%
Income of the respondents		
Below Rs.2,00,000	32	16%
Rs.2,00,001-Rs.4,00,000	70	35%
Rs.4,00,001-Rs.6,00,000	57	28.5%
AboveRs.6,00,001	41	20.5%
Marital status of the respondent		
Married	81	40.5%
Unmarried	119	59.5%
Type of the family of the respondent		
Joint family	57	28.5%
Nuclear family	143	71.5%
No of Family members of the respondent		
Below 2 members	11	5.5%
2-4 members	114	57%
4-6 members	51	25.5%
Above 6 members	24	12%
No of Earning Members in family		
1	39	19.5%
2	103	51.5%
3	45	22.5%
Above 3	13	6.5%
Annual savings in the family		
Below Rs. 20,000	32	16%
Rs. 20,001 – 40,000	75	37.5%
Rs. 40,001 – 50,000	56	28%
Above Rs. 50,000	37	18.5%
Residential Status		
Urban	91	45.5%
Semi- urban	87	43.5%
Rural	22	11%

Source: Primary Data

From the above table highlighted that 52.5% of the respondents are male. 62.5% of the respondents belong to the age group of below 30 years. 65% of the respondents are qualified with UG/PG level of education. 34% of the respondents are private employees. 59.5% of the respondents are unmarried. 71.5% of the respondents are living in nuclear family. 57% of the respondents have 2 - 4 members in their family. 35% of the respondents have an annual income between Rs.2,00,001-Rs.4,00,000. 51.5% of the respondents have 2 earning members in their family. 37.5% of the respondents save an amount between Rs.20,001– 40,000. 45.5% of the respondents are living in Urban areas.

Table 2 – Type of Investment pattern preferred other than Insurance

S. No	Type of LIC Policy	Respondents

	Purchased	Yes		No	
		Yes	%	No	%
1	Bank Fixed Deposit	137	68.5	63	31.5
2	Chit Funds	79	39.5	121	60.5
3	Post office savings	110	55	90	45
4	Land	136	68	64	32
5	Gold	141	70.5	59	29.5

Source: Primary data

Table 2 shows that out of the total respondents taken for the study, 141 (70.5%) respondents prefer to invest in gold, 137 (68.5%) respondents prefer to invest in bank fixed deposits, 136 (68%) respondents prefer to invest in land, 121 (60.5%) respondents do not prefer to invest in chit funds and 110 (55%) respondents prefer to invest in post office savings.

Table 3 – The Primary Reason of the respondents for purchasing an LIC policy

S. No	Primary Reasons	Respondents	
		Number	Percentage (%)
1	Tax Benefits	34	17
2	Investment Opportunities	61	30.5
3	Insurance Coverage	77	38.5
4	Retirement Planning	28	14
	Total	200	100

Source: Primary Data

Table 3 reveals that out of the total respondents taken for the study, 77(38.5%) respondents prefer to buy an insurance policy for coverage, 61 (30.5%) respondents prefer to buy an insurance policy for investment opportunities, 34 (17%) respondents prefer to buy an insurance policy for tax benefits and 28 (14%) respondents prefer to buy an insurance policy for the purpose of retirement plans.

Table 4 – Source of Influence of the respondents

S. No	Source of Influence	Respondents	
		Number	Percentage(%)
1	Media	20	10
2	Insurance Agents	58	29
3	Government	38	19
4	Friends, family & colleagues	84	42
	Total	200	100

Source: Primary Data

Table 4 depicts that out of the total respondents taken for the study, 84 (42%) respondents were influenced by friends, family & colleagues, 58 (29%) respondents were influenced by insurance agents, 38 (19%) respondents were influenced by government and 20(10%) respondents were influenced by the media to get an insurance policy.

Table 5 -Number of Years with LIC by the Respondents

S. No	No. of Years	Respondents	
		Number	Percentage (%)
1	Lessthan1year	40	20
2	1– 3years	98	49
3	3– 5years	50	25
4	More than 5 years	12	06
	Total	200	100

Source: Primary Data

Table 5 shows that out of the total respondents taken for the study, 98(49%) respondents have been policyholders with LIC for 1–5years, 50(25%) respondents for 5–10 years, 40(20%) respondents have been policyholders with LIC for a period less than 1 year and 12 (6%) respondents have been policyholders with LIC for more than 10 years.

Table 6 - Factors influence to purchase an LIC Policy

S. No	Factors	Respondents								Total	Score	Rank
		Level	P-1	P-2	P-3	P-4	P-5	P-6	P-7			
		Score	7	6	5	4	3	2	1			
1	Risk	Level	66	31	50	19	6	17	11	200	5.49	I
		Score	462	186	250	76	18	34	11	1099		
2	Bonus	Level	24	64	45	29	22	12	4	200	4.87	II
		Score	168	372	225	116	66	24	4	975		
3	Premium	Level	23	35	69	39	18	11	5	200	4.76	III
		Score	161	210	345	156	54	22	5	953		
4	Savings	Level	26	35	40	48	25	12	14	200	4.48	V
		Score	182	210	200	192	75	24	14	897		
5	Tax benefits	Level	25	29	51	38	34	13	10	200	4.47	VI
		Score	175	174	255	152	102	26	10	894		
6	Maturity Value	Level	23	43	46	28	24	29	7	200	4.49	IV
		Score	161	258	230	112	72	58	7	898		

7	Loan facility	Level	30	24	50	21	27	22	26	200	4.19	VII
		Score	210	144	250	84	81	44	26	839		

Source: Primary Data

Table 6 highlighted that the majority of the respondents indicate that, risk is the main factor influencing consumers towards LIC policies. This ranks first according to the score obtained (Score=5.49). Bonus of LIC policies is the second most influencing factor, according to the scores obtained (Score=4.87). Premium of LIC policies is the third most influencing factor, according to the scores obtained (Score=4.76). Maturity value of LIC policies is the fourth most influencing factor, according to the scores obtained (Score= 4.49). Savings of LIC policies is the fifth most influencing factor, according to the scores obtained (Score=4.48). Tax benefits of LIC policies is the sixth most influencing factor, according to the scores obtained (Score =4.47). Loan facility of LIC policies is the least influencing factor, according to the scores obtained (Score=4.19).

Table 8 - Type of LIC Policy Purchased by the respondents

S. No	Type of LIC Policy Purchased	Respondents			
		Yes	%	No	%
1	Endowment Policy	119	59.5	81	40.5
2	Term Policy	94	47	106	53
3	Money- back Policy	114	57	86	43
4	Unit Linked Insurance Policy	74	37	126	63

Source: Primary Data

Table 7 shows that out of the total respondents taken for study, 119 (59.5%) respondents have purchased endowment policy, 114 (57%) respondents have chosen moneyback policies, 94 (47%) respondents have opted for term policies and 74 (37%) respondents have invested to unit linked insurance policies.

Table 8 - Type of plan preferred by the respondents

S. No	Type of Plans	Respondents	
		Number	Percentage (%)
1	Low risk with secured and low returns	55	27.5
2	Moderate risk with moderate returns	113	56.5
3	High risk with high returns	32	16
	Total	200	100

Source: Primary Data

Table 8 shows that out of the total respondents taken for the study, 113 (56.5%) respondents prefer to take moderate risk plans with moderate returns, 55 (27.5%) respondents prefer to take low risk plans with low returns and 32 (16%) respondents prefer to take high risk plans with high returns.

Table 9 - LIC Policies compared with Private Insurance Companies

S. No	Level	Respondents
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		Number	Percentage (%)
1	Strongly Agree	32	16
2	Agree	70	35
3	Neutral	66	33
4	Disagree	28	14
5	Strongly Disagree	04	02
	Total	200	100

Source: Primary Data

Table 9 reveals that out of the total respondents taken for the study, 70 (35%) respondents have agreed that LIC policies are more attractive than policies of private insurance companies, 66 (33%) have neutral opinion, 32 (16%) respondents have strongly agreed, 28 (14%) respondents have disagreed and 4 (2%) respondents have strongly disagreed.

Table 10 - Kind of issues faced during claim settlement process by the respondents

S. No	Kind of issues faced during Claim Settlement Process	Respondents	
		Number	Percentage (%)
1	Delay in claim settlement	22	21
2	Insufficient claim settlement	17	16
3	Claim rejection	61	58
4	Others	5	5
	Total	105	100

Source: Primary Data

Table 10 depicts that out of the 105 respondents taken for the study, 61 (58%) respondents face issues of claim rejection, 22 (21%) respondents face issues of delay in claim settlement, 17 (16%) respondents face issues of insufficient claim settlement and 5 (5%) respondents face other issues.

Table 11 - Level of Satisfaction of LIC Policies by the respondents

S. No	Parameters	Respondents					Total	Score	Rank	
		Level	P-1	P-2	P-3	P-4				P-5
		Score	5	4	3	2				1
1.	Risk	Level	65	49	63	13	10	200	3.73	III
		Score	325	196	189	26	10			
2.	Bonus	Level	20	99	54	17	10	200	3.51	IV
		Score	100	396	162	34	10			
3.	Premium	Level	24	57	81	26	12	200	4.13	I
		Score	120	399	243	52	12			
4.	Savings	Level	31	67	58	31	13	200	3.36	V
		Score	155	268	174	62	13			
5.	Tax benefits	Level	24	57	68	27	24	200	3.85	II
		Score	120	228	204	194	24			
6.	Maturity Value	Level	25	67	56	32	20	200	3.22	VI
		Score	125	268	168	64	20			
7.	Loan facility	Level	30	44	83	25	18	200	3.21	VII
		Score	150	176	249	50	18			

Source: Primary Data

Table 11 depicts that the majority of the respondents indicate that premium is the main parameter for the level of satisfaction in LIC policies. This ranks first according to the score obtained (Score = 4.13). Tax Benefits of LIC policies is the second most satisfied factor. This ranks second according to the scores obtained (Score = 3.85). Risk of LIC policies is the third most satisfied factor. This ranks third according to the scores obtained (Score = 3.73). Bonus of LIC policies is the fourth most satisfied factor. This ranks fourth according to the scores obtained (Score = 3.51). Savings of LIC policies is the fifth most satisfied factor. This ranks fifth according to the scores obtained (Score = 3.36). Maturity Value of LIC policies is the sixth most satisfied factor. This ranks sixth according to the scores obtained (Score = 3.22). Loan facility of LIC policies is the least satisfied factor. This ranks seventh according to the scores obtained (Score = 3.21).

FINDINGS

- Majority (52.5%) 105 respondents are male
- Majority (62.5%) are below 30 years of age
- Majority (65%) of the respondents are qualified with UG/PG level of education
- Most (22.5%) of the respondents are private employees
- Most (35%) of the respondents have annual income between Rs.2,00,001 - Rs.4,00,000
- Majority (59.5%) respondents are unmarried
- Majority (71.5%) respondents are of nuclear family
- Majority (57%) of the respondents have 2 - 4 members in the family
- Majority (51.5%) of the respondents have 2 earning members in their family
- Most (37.5%) of the respondents save in the range of Rs.20,001 – 40,000
- Most (45.5%) of the respondents are living in Urban areas
- Majority (70.5%) of the respondents prefer to invest in gold
- Most (38.5%) of the respondents have purchased insurance policy for the purpose of insurance coverage
- Most (42%) of the respondents were influenced by friends, family and colleagues to get an insurance policy
- Most (39%) of the respondents have a policy duration of 1-3 years
- Majority of the respondents have given top preference to risk as the High influencing factor among others in buying LIC policy
- Majority (59.5%) of the respondents have purchased endowment policy
- Majority (56.5%) of the respondents prefer moderate risk plans
- Most (35%) of the respondents agree that LIC policies are more attractive than policies of private insurance companies
- Majority (58%) respondents face issues of claim rejection
- Premium is the highest level of satisfaction in LIC policies.

CONCLUSION

Life insurance is an important form of insurance and essential for every individual. India is a developing country where income levels of the people are increasing with increased opportunity. Customers are the real pillars of success of life insurance business and thus it is necessary to keep their policyholders satisfied and retain them as long as possible. The study reveals that risk is the main factor influencing the customer towards LIC policy. The study also found that majority of the customers feel investment as tax saving option. The study concluded that major influencing factors in choosing an insurance company in the future are supposed to be company image and lower premium.

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